

EDCSPROOF – ENERGY DEMAND CONTROL SYSTEM

“The expected project result is a broadly applicable, cross-sectoral energy concept for subsequent implementation at project partners’ sites, and for a large majority of companies. Energy efficiency and thus the competitiveness of the manufacturing industry will be increased, the share of renewable energies raised, and Austria’s pioneering role strengthened.”

BERND WINDHOLZ,
Project Manager EDCsproof, Austrian Institute of Technology

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EDCSproof develops a future concept for the decarbonization of industrial energy supply systems through the possibilities of digitalization. The focus is on online, predictive and holistic, reconfigurable control. The concept is optimized in the laboratory, its scalability and application possibilities for different branches of industry are examined in a technical-economic and ecological evaluation.

KEY FACTS

CO₂ savings potential of
350,000 tons per year in
Austria

Duration: 10/18 – 12/21

Project volume: €1,591,463

MAIN GOALS

Integration of renewables through energy storages

Waste heat recovery through high-temperature heat pumps (<150°C)

Online, predictive and holistic, reconfigurable control concept

Flexible industrial participants in power grids

kleinkraft

evon

